

Semantic Segmentation in Self-Driving Cars Using Pyramid Parsing Network (PSPNet) on Cityscape Dataset

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Article History:

Received: 08.01.2025 Revised: 28.01.2025 Accepted: 01.02.2025 Published: 02.02.2025

ABSTRACT:

Semantic segmentation has been one of the must research topics in the field of computer vision in recent years. This study was conducted using U-Net architecture in the context of self-driving cars on a cityscape dataset. The dataset is an urban scene image that contains all scene scenarios in a typical city. It includes 5,000 high-quality finely annotated pixel-level images gathered from 50 cities over various seasons. The proposed PSPNet model uses a pre-trained ResNet101 for feature extraction. We used a pyramid pooling of (1x1), (2x2), (3x3) and (6x6). We further used augmentation techniques to make the model learn more features of both the major and minor classes. The model achieved 90% accuracy, 83% pixel accuracy, 90% precision, 88% recall and 89% F1 score metric. The model was trained for 75 epochs of 3 hours of training time on the cityscape dataset. The model has shown good performance by achieving high accuracy and addressing class imbalance in the context of autonomous driving. Therefore, we concluded that PSPNet with ResNet101 as the backbone achieved high accuracy compared to the state-of-the-art model and addressed the issue of class imbalance.

Keywords: Autonomous Vehicles, Cityscape dataset, Semantic Segmentation, ResNet101.

Suggested Citation: E.A. Sowe, M.F. Sanyang, W. Yahya, H.G. Gegbe, "Semantic Segmentation in Self-Driving Cars Using Pyramid Parsing Network (PSPNet) on Cityscape Dataset," *Eur. J. Appl. Sc. Eng. Technol.*, vol. 3(1), pp. 87-98, Jan-Feb 2025. DOI: 10.59324/ejaset.2025.3(1).07

INTRODUCTION

Semantic segmentation plays an important role in enabling autonomous vehicles, such as self-driving cars, to understand and navigate their surroundings smoothly and effectively. Autonomous cars, sometimes referred to as driverless vehicles [1], autonomous vehicles [3,4], or robotic cars [2],

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are among the most exciting new technologies at the moment and a hot topic of study. It is a widely used perception method for self-driving cars that associates each pixel of an image with a predefined class [16]. Compared to image recognition and target location and detection, semantic segmentation provides object classification information and extracts location information, laying the foundation for other computer vision tasks [17,18]. The achievement of high accuracy and computational efficiency in semantic segmentation is essential for the safe and efficient operation of autonomous vehicles.

A self-driving car can understand its environment and operate with less human intervention [12]. For autonomous driving to be successful, cars must be able to collect and process data from their surroundings in real-time using cameras and sensors to create a complete picture of driving conditions [5]. These cars mainly depend on the information collected by their sensors [6]. These cars use a variety of advanced sensors, cameras, and computer vision algorithms to perceive their environment and make decisions.

Convolutional neural networks (CNN) and other deep learning techniques have recently been used to achieve sophisticated results in image segmentation and classification [5-9]. These networks are made up of layers that can learn the information's understructure from multilevel data. Since the characteristics that make up these layers are learned from the data and do not require human design, deep learning techniques can efficiently extract features independently, saving time and effort [14]. CNNs have shown good results in medical analysis, such as segmentation of brain tumors [10], liver tumors [11], and pancreatic tumors [12], as well as in computer-aided diagnostic applications [13] to improve body.

Achieving high accuracy performance and addressing class imbalance causing the state-of-the-art models such as FCN[35] and SegNet [36] to ignore small important details has long been a challenge. As a result, semantic segmentation approaches are biased towards the dominant classes during inference [15]. This paper implemented a widely used architecture on scene parsing known as PSPNet on a cityscape dataset for semantic segmentation in the context of autonomous driving. By adapting this architecture to the cityscape dataset, we demonstrated that the model has great accuracy in semantic segmentation tasks outperforming the state-of-the-art model FCN[35] and SegNet [36], which are critical for autonomous vehicles to understand their surroundings. Using a pre-trained ResNet101, which has 101 layers for efficient feature extraction within the PSPNet model, the study delivered good segmentation results, making it particularly well-suited for complex scenes.

The key contributions of the paper include the following:

1. The use of a PSPNet model in a cityscape dataset to improve accuracy and address class imbalance.
2. The use of ResNet101 as the CNN(Convolutional Network) backbone for better feature extraction as compared to ResNet50 and VGG16 of the state-of-the-art models.
3. The use of augmentation techniques such as flipping, rotation, random cropping and Gaussian blur to increase the variety of representation of the minority classes.

RELATED TOPICS

Deep Learning for Image Segmentation

The main goal of the U-Net architecture was to address the issues of limited data in the medical field. It was designed to effectively analyze a smaller amount of data while maintaining computational effectiveness. Due to its versatility, it can also be used in CamVid and cityscape datasets to perform well. Other models, such as PSPNet proposed by Hengshuang Zhao et al. [25] in the paper titled "Pyramid Scene Parsing Network" presented at CVPR 2017, had a remarkable performance. The model uses a pre-trained ResNet50 for feature extraction. This pre-trained are trained on the ImageNet dataset for classification tasks. This model classified a segmented object to the contextual information available within the surroundings. Other deep learning models use encoder-decoder, these types include fully convolutional networks (FCN) [5], encoder-decoder-based techniques such

as Segnet [26], ERFNet [27], and U-Net [28], as well as ESPnetv2 [29].

Attention and Gating Mechanism

CNNs have recently improved in various vision tasks, including classification [16], detection [17], segmentation [18], image captioning [19], and visual recognition [20] using attention mechanisms. Attention processes guide the model helping it focus on the most important features and ignoring those not relevant to a particular task. To capture long-range dependencies, Wang et al. [16] presented a residual attention network that uses non-local self-attention processes. Hu et al. [21] introduced the squeeze-and-excitation method for ILSVRC 2017 image classification with channel-wise attention computed to emphasize the valuable channels via global average pooling and surpassed the existing methods. An interesting work on self-attention was presented by Woo et al. [22], wherein they proposed a convolutional block attention module (CBAM) that leverages both spatial and channel information allowing for effective feature refinement.

Other Variants and Modifications

The Dilated-UNet model improves medical image segmentation by utilizing the advantages of the U-Net architecture and the Dilated Transformer blocks [23]. The Dilated Transformer blocks help to portray a bigger background without compromising detail.

Attention U-Net [23] is a version that integrates an attention gate to improve feature selection during segmentation, increasing sensitivity and prediction accuracy, especially in complex image contexts.

Challenges and Existing Problems

Achieving a high accuracy performance has long been a challenge. Specifically, ENet [31] and Fast-SCNN [32] aim to address this gap in speed and accuracy with their lightweight architectures; a crucial area for robotics, self-driving cars, and aerial vehicles, but these issues still exist.

Another challenge is a class imbalance in semantic segmentation training datasets. Certain kinds of items (such as roads and automobiles) may dominate the dataset, resulting in a model that excels at segmenting common objects but struggles with less common categories such as cyclists or pedestrians (particularly in rural regions). This lack of robustness can undermine the reliability and safety of autonomous vehicles [30]. This bias might cause significant performance disparities when facing unusual circumstances on the road, jeopardizing autonomous vehicle safety and operational dependability.

To address these challenges, we proposed a PSPNet model with a ResNet101 backbone, which has 101 layers suitable for feature extraction, thus achieving high accuracy and addressing the issue of class imbalance on the Cityscape dataset. We also used augmentation techniques including flipping, rotation, scaling, and random cropping to increase the variety and representation of minority classes so that the model becomes robust to such class variations. We further used a categorical cross-entropy loss function for multi-class problems. The loss function treated each class as

METHODOLOGY

Dataset

The Cityscape dataset is an urban scene dataset that contains all scene scenarios in a typical city. It includes 5,000 high-quality finely annotated pixel-level images gathered from 50 cities taken over various seasons. For training, validation and testing, the images are separated into sets with the numbers 2,975, 500, and 1,525. Identifies 19 categories or classes that include both things and junk [14]. In addition, two comparison settings are given, training with only fine data or training with both fine and coarse data, 20,000 coarsely annotated images [25]. The dataset supported and our experimental goal. The dataset supported the experiment goal by dealing with various issues in semantic segmentation like the accuracy of understanding an entire scene and scene context, which are important for advancing research into self-driving cars as well as urban scene understanding. The dataset offers high-quality images that are meticulously annotated with pixel-precise labels. Detailed annotations allow for precise evaluation of models' performance. There are various

scenarios, including lighting conditions, weather, times of day, and scenes containing multiple objects. This allows models to generalize well and understand more in varied conditions, thus self-driving cars can work well. It includes a variety of urban scenes with a range of object kinds and occlusions.

Data Preprocessing

Download and Resize: Firstly, the dataset is downloaded and uploaded to the Kaggle cloud environment for storage and processing. The images are then resized to 200x256 pixels and stored in their respective directories of test, validation and training.

Normalization and Dataset creation: The images are then normalized between the range of [0,1] by dividing by 255.0 into three channels known as the RGB color standardization.

$$image_{norm} = clip\left(\frac{image}{255.0}, 0.0, 1.0\right) \quad (1)$$

Data Augmentation

(1) Random Horizontal and Vertical Flip

The images are then flip horizontally and vertically with a probability of 50%.

$$I'(x, y) = I(W - x - 1, y) \quad (2)$$

$$I'(x, y) = I(x, H - y - 1) \quad (3)$$

2) Random Rotation

The images are rotated by a random angle, within a specified range rotation by -10 and 10 degrees for each pixel location (x,y)(x,y) is transformed.

$$x' = x \cos(\theta) - y \sin(\theta) \quad (4)$$

$$y' = x \sin(\theta) + y \cos(\theta) \quad (5)$$

3) Gaussian Blur

Blurs the image using a Gaussian kernel, it is in smoothing out noise and small details. The Gaussian kernel of size k×k and standard deviation σ

$$G(x, y) = \frac{1}{2\pi\sigma^2} \exp\left(-\frac{x^2+y^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) \quad (6)$$

Model Architecture

In this section, we used the Pyramid Scene Parsing Network (PSPNet) to address the challenges of semantic segmentation by capturing both local and global context information in images. It was originally introduced by Zhao et al. (2017)[25], and it is excellent for its Pyramid Pooling Module (PPM) that aggregates contextual information from multiple spatial scales. This makes it well-suited for scene-parsing tasks in complex scene environments, specifically the cityscape dataset in the context of autonomous driving. Local feature extraction and global scene awareness must be balanced, especially in autonomous driving, where judgements rely on knowledge of the surrounding environment as well as the immediate road layout. It has multiscale pooling capability, thus PSPNet effectively encodes diverse spatial information, This is critical for segmenting road elements, vehicles, pedestrians, and other scene components.

The model uses the ResNet101 backbone as its feature extractor. The ResNet101 model, pre-trained on ImageNet, is adapted to extract high-level feature maps from the input images and it has 101 layers. The ResNet101 model (Residual Neural Network with 101 layers) is a prominent architecture in deep learning. It is known for its effectiveness in image classification tasks. Because of the deep residual learning incorporated into its architecture, deep networks may be trained without encountering typical problems like disappearing gradients. To more effectively use learn characteristics for the next tasks, it has been trained using the ImageNet dataset.

Many convolutional layers, batch normalisation, and ReLU activation functions are among the 101 layers that comprise the model's deep architecture and are effective for feature extractions in a complex scene environment. One of the most important components of ResNet101 is the usage of skip connections. Bypassing one or more levels and adding the input to the output of a subsequent layer is made possible by the skip connection. This architectural choice enables more efficient gradient back-propagation during training. This is important to maintain the model performance as depth increases.

These feature maps serve as the foundation for the subsequent pyramid pooling operations, this includes the red pooling(1x1), yellow pooling(2x2), blue pooling(3x3)and green pooling(6x6). With its 101 layers, ResNet101's structure offers the ability to extract rich features. This operation is crucial for complex scenes in autonomous cars. We further refined the RestNet101 backbone with additional convolutional layers to ensure compatibility with the segmentation task. The difficulties of domain adaption and the particular needs of road scene parsing, like identifying overlapping or obscured items are addressed in this preprocessing stage.

Figure 1. Pyramid Parsing Network Model

Source: [25]

Loss Function

The categorical loss function is a common choice for multiclass semantic segmentation. Classifies each pixel with a distinct color of multiple objects in a single image. As a result, this loss function calculates the difference between the data's true distribution and the model's expected distribution

output.

$$L = - \sum_{i=1}^C y_i \log (p_i) \tag{7}$$

Where:

C is the number of classes.

y_i is the binary indicator (0 or 1) if class label i is the correct classification for a sample.

p_i is the predicted probability that the sample belongs to class i .

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The model has shown some notable results 90% model accuracy, 83% of pixel accuracy, 88% of recall accuracy, precision of 90% and F1 score of 89%. This has shown that ResNet101 can be used for feature extraction as an encoder. Fig4 shows the original, masked, and output of the predicted image on the cityscape dataset. Thus, we address the class imbalance and achieve high accuracy.

Figure 2. Proposed Model Results on the Cityscape Dataset

Figure 3. PSPNet Accuracy Curve

Figure 4. Proposed PSPNet Model Loss

Evaluation Metrics

(1) Pixel Accuracy: A common Pixel evaluation metric is used to further assess the model. It calculates the percentage of the correctly identified pixels across all given classes, providing a simple but effective method for evaluating the overall performance of the model. Our model obtained 83%. The equation for Pixel Accuracy is given by:

$$Pixel\ Accuracy = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N 1(\hat{y}_i=y_i)}{N} \quad (8)$$

Where:

N is defined as the total number of pixels in the image or across all images in the cityscape dataset.

\hat{y}_i is the predicted label for the pixel y_i .

y_i stands for the true label for the pixel y_i .

$1(\hat{y}_i = y_i)$ is the indicator function that equals 1 if the predicted label \hat{y}_i matches the true label y_i , and 0 otherwise.

Figure 5. Pixel Accuracy Metric

(2) Precision

Precision is the percentage of real positive pixels among all pixels labelled as positive by the model. It is an essential metric, particularly in circumstances where false positives might have serious consequences, such as in medical diagnostic applications and autonomous systems [33]. A high precision score indicates that a model reliably identifies the relevant pixels, minimizing instances of falsely labelling background pixels as part of the target class [34]. Our model obtained 90% precision.

Figure 6. Precision Metric

(3) Recall

We further used the Recall evaluation metric to further assessed our model by measuring the percentage of real positive samples that the model accurately detected. Thus, our model achieved 88% recall accuracy.

$$Recall = \frac{True\ Positives\ (TP)}{True\ Positives\ (TP) + False\ Negatives\ (FN)} \quad (9)$$

Figure 7. Recall Evaluation Metric

(4) F1 Score

We further analyzed with F1 score which is a harmonic

mean of precision and recall, providing a balanced evaluation metric for our proposed model, where there are imbalance class distributions. We obtained an 89% F1 Score.

$$F1 = 2 \cdot \frac{Precision \cdot Recall}{Precision + Recall} \quad (10)$$

Figure 8. F1 Score Evaluation Metric

Table 1. Comparison of Our Model with State-of-the-Art Models Performance in (%)

Model	Accuracy	Pixel Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 Score
DeepLabV3+ [37]	88.3	92	87.1	88.5	88.5
FCN [35]	-	73.34	83	81	82
SegNet [36]	83.7	71.00	84	81	82
U-Net++ [38]	87.1	91	86.3	87	86.6
Proposed PSPNet	90	83	90	88	89

Table 2. Per Class Performance on Cityscape Dataset in (%)

Class	Class Accuracy	Pixel Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 Score
Road	98.5	90	93	91	92
Sidewalk	95.1	88	89	92	90.5
Building	97	91	94	92	93
Wall	94.5	89.0	91.0	87.0	89.0
Fence	89.0	84.0	83.0	82	82.5
Pole	96.2	88.0	90.0	89.0	89.5
Traffic Light	93.4	91.0	88.0	92.0	90.0
Traffic sign	95.3	86.0	91.0	92.0	91.0
Vegetation	98.0	94.0	95.0	93.0	94.0
Terrain	94.3	86.0	88.0	87.0	87.0
Sky	98.0	95.0	98.0	97.0	97.0
Person	96.5	92.0	96.0	93.0	94.0
Rider	95.8	90.0	94.0	93.0	94.0
Car	97.0	95.0	96.0	94.0	95.0
Truck	93.3	87.0	91.0	89.0	90.0
Bus	96.0	91.0	93.0	91.0	92.0
Train	97.4	93.0	96.0	92.0	94.0
Motorcycle	94.3	86.0	87.0	85.0	86.0
Bicycle	93.7	84.0	88.0	86.0	87.0

CONCLUSION

The proposed model successfully extracts detailed and contextually important information from images in a complex scene of the Cityscape dataset by utilizing the pre-trained ResNet101 architecture for feature extraction. We obtained 90% accuracy, 90% precision, 83% pixel accuracy, 88% recall and 89% F1 score. The model was trained over 75 epochs for 3 hours on the cityscape dataset.

Metrics indicate that our method reduced class imbalance and delivered an accurate, consistent performance for all classes. Classes with more frequency, i.e., "Road" and "Sky" obtained F1 scores of 92% and 97% respectively; whereas difficult, minority classes "Fence" and "Truck" also performed comparatively well with F1 scores of 82.5% and 90% respectively.

The study findings provide validation that data augmentation and categorical loss functions help to handle class imbalance, allowing the model for reliable performance over a large number of semantic categories. Fairness and robustness thus provided by this, is essential for semantic segmentation to be applied in real-world scenarios. The model effectively handles the inherent limitations of urban settings by achieving high precision and addressing class imbalance. The model therefore outperforms the state-of-art models FCN [35] and SegNet [36].

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